

POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

The article considers digital technologies implementation in the field of education. It also analyses technology -assisted learning that facilitates and enhances foreign language teaching. The issue of integrating these advanced technologies into educational process is considered.

Key words: innovations, advanced technologies, implementation, interactive teaching methods, distance learning, digital technology, integrating the internet.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is a time of new challenges for humanity or a time of new social, cultural, personal and other attitudes formation. First of all, this time is characterized by the presence of such a phenomenon as globalization. Globalization is the trump card for the rapid development across the globe in language, culture, tradition, customs, lifestyle, economy, science, and technology. Globalization and English language work as pull factors for one another.

Uzbekistan, like other countries, is becoming more and more involved in shaping the global information society. It is well-known that Internet now is growing, it represents one of the most successful examples of the benefits of sustained investment and commitment to research and develop information infrastructure, and year by year, digital technology is becoming a more formidable force. The modern age is the era of knowledge explosion. This explosion has become possible due to the progress of science and technology. The use of science and technology in the field of communication has revolutionized the whole world. Currently, the implementation of innovative and effective teaching methods in all educational institutions is becoming an urgent task. In particular, the use of new technologies and other navigation methods in reading, learning and teaching foreign languages has been successful. At the same time, there are many innovations in the way of teaching foreign languages. Their implementation and results provide positive evidence that the interest in the learning

process is increasing. It is important to pay attention to student learning activities, when selecting and implementing elements of educational technologies.

DISCUSSION

The modern education system is increasingly using digital technologies as one of the pressing problems of modern teaching foreign languages method is the orientation of the entire educational process towards the active independent work of students and the creation of conditions for their self-study and self-expression. The educational space today is technology - based educational programs, in the development of which experienced teachers, programmers, psychologists and designers take part. They are a good help in learning, and they orient students to a free and independent pace of learning. Control of knowledge is a guarantee of transition to a new level. Thus, the digital technology provides us with:

- Interactivity
- Multimedia
- Modeling
- Communication
- Productivity

Simultaneous participation of teachers and digital technologies in the educational process improves the quality of education, so this collaboration on the one hand, helps students of different categories better understanding the teaching material. The use of the proposed method enhances the teaching process, increases students' interest in the subject, and enables them to deepen their learning material. So, it places much higher requirements for a teacher qualification and training. It is now necessary not only to master traditional teaching methods, but also to upgrade learners by using science and technology, depending on the nature of the learners. The last step in the use of the technology is connecting to the network and teaching and learning via the Internet. It is now an integral part of the information technology system with the interconnected computers being the main link in it. Due to equipping educational institutions with powerful digital technology and the development of the Internet community, the distance education system is developing as well. The Internet provides a wide variety of material used for teaching and learning a foreign language. It requires careful filtering and potential changes for efficient use of these materials in the distance learning program. On the development of online resources for teaching a foreign language in a distance learning program consider some factors. They are: basic characteristics of the distance learning method, guidelines for teaching and studying a foreign language, importance of content, needs of learners and types of their study.

Such elements describe a variety of strategies implemented in developing teaching materials. Taken approaches will enable efficient processing of information, promote effective learning and engagement, and inspire students. Materials need to be organized and presented in such a way that they can be adapted to different needs and requirements, as well on language skill levels. Electronic materials for teaching a foreign language in a distance learning system can be structured by skills, with sections for reading, writing, listening, and speaking. The biggest benefit of the distance learning program on the improvement of speech skills is the ability to produce a recording. Students can listen to, evaluate and re-record before a suitable standard is reached. In this way, students can admit the details and identify acceptable and relevant language types and components.

Successful implementation of the modernization program is often based on digital technology enable students to use information based on the ability to see, to read and to hear this information. So, all educational facilities should provide modern technology, and organizers of the education system should have enough knowledge in the area. Now everyone understands that the Internet has tremendous information capabilities. But, whatever properties a particular teaching tool possesses, didactic tasks are primary. And the cognitive activity of students is especially important due to certain educational goals, and that's why, the new technology with all its capabilities and resources is one of the means of realizing these goals and objectives.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence. For this purpose, teachers can:

- include network materials in the content of the lesson (integrating them into the curriculum);
- conduct an independent search for information by students as part of the project;
- increase motivation and create the need for learning a foreign language through live communication;
- form and develop reading skills, directly using network materials of varying degrees of complexity;
- form and develop listening skills based on authentic audio texts of the Internet, also, accordingly, prepared by the teacher;
- improve writing skills by writing answers to correspondence partners;
- replenish vocabulary with the vocabulary of the modern foreign language, which reflects a certain stage in the development of culture, social and political structure of society, using authentic texts;
- obtain knowledge, including speech etiquette, features of the speech behavior of various peoples in the conditions of communication, features of culture, and traditions of the country.

CONCLUSION

It should be concluded that modern technologies allow us to achieve the level of education, its quality and especially efficiency in educational institutions, which correspond to the world standards. Technology integration into educational process is viewed as a crucial element that needs to be addressed at the university level. So, systematic plans for integrating technology into the classroom teaching must be developed. Thus, the process of teaching English as a foreign language should be reviewed and optimized taking into account the trends in the development of intercultural communication in a multicultural world.

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